

Comparison of the chemical peeling of retinoic acid and mandelic acid on oiliness and hyperchromia after acne in adult women: a randomized clinical trial

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ABSTRACT Aim: to compare self-satisfaction and discomfort in the application of two types of chemical facial peeling. **Methods:** Randomized and controlled clinical trial consisting of 30 women with moderate facial hyperpigmentation randomly divided into 03 groups M- mandelic acid 30%, Group R - retinoic acid at 05%, L- mechanical face exfoliation. The evaluations were performed in the 1st and 6th weeks by the blind investigator about photography and evaluation of skin texture. They were evaluated through self-report: self-satisfaction by the GAIS scale, and the discomfort index. **Results:** There was a significant difference in the M and R groups compared to the L group about the GAIS scale (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p < 0.002$; Dunn post-test, $p < 0.05$) and photographic evaluation (ANOVA one route, $p = 0.034$, Sudent-Newman-Keuls post-test, $p < 0.05$). Regarding the discomfort score, there was a difference between the M versus R group (Friedman test, $p = 0.002$). **Conclusion:** Both protocols obtained beneficial and similar effects among themselves.

KEYWORDS Acne vulgaris, Hyperpigmentation, Chemexfoliation

Introduction

Acne vulgaris is a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous system caused by follicular hyperkeratosis. This leads to obstruction of the pilosebaceous canal, resulting in inflammation and, subsequently, the formation of comedones, papules and pustules, nodules and scars [1]. Sun exposure in individuals with acne may cause postinflammatory changes due to the increased secretory activity of melanocytes, generating spots of brown color[2]. About 85% of the general population has common acne or acne scars in their lives, which mainly included on the face, back and chest[3]. Post-acne hyperpigmentations can negatively influence the individual's quality of life, so it is necessary to deal with these complications to prevent emotional consequences and repercussions on the quality of life and self-esteem[4].

The procedures of superficial chemical abrasion are commonly used in the treatment of photoaging[5], active acne[9], post-acne[7] hyperchromias, melasma[8] among other skin problems, such as a simple procedure performed by dermatologists, plastic surgeons and, more recently, specialist physiotherapists [9,10].

The use of superficial chemical peels aims to accelerate the exfoliation process of the epidermis, increasing the activity of enzymes that lead to epidermolysis. The best results are obtained with serial applications, performed at short intervals; the desquamation is usually thin and clear, does not alter the daily routine of the patient, lighten spots and attenuate fine wrinkles, and stimulate the renewal of collagen[11]. The acid retinoic acid vitamin A or even known as tretinoin, is a liposoluble substance, for medical use only. Topical retinoic acid has been used successfully for many years in the treatment of acne, melasma, and post-inflammatory hyperchromias. Its main mechanisms of action are: compression of the corneal layer, increased collagen synthesis. Stimulate keratinocytes to improve the distribution of melanocytes and to produce a normalization of the epidermis; eliminates atypical keratinocytes and increases neovascularization of the dermis[12].

Mandelic acid derived from bitter almond extract is one of the

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highest molecular weight alpha hydroxy acids (AHAs), therefore, it is used to treat hyperpigmentation as a depigmenting peeling, favoring a uniform effect. The properties of this acid comprise the alteration of the intercellular connections, promoting a reduction of the cohesion between the corneocytes, desquamation of the corneous layer and stimulation of the production of new cells to a greater or lesser degree, depending on their structures¹³. It is an AHA that at a concentration of 20 to 30% is used for superficial peeling procedures in the office. However, its use is not widespread and there are few controlled clinical trials using this AH^{8,14}. In despite, the aim of this study is to evaluate the aesthetic self-satisfaction and tolerability of the session with chemical peeling and mechanical exfoliation of the face in adult women with moderate post-acne hyperpigmentation. In addition to compare two types of chemical agents, retinoic acid and mandelic acid.

Materials and Methods

The study consisted of an initial sample of 56 volunteers recruited during the months of September 2016 to September 2017. All of them were invited to participate in the survey via telephone contact. However, eighteen did not meet the inclusion criteria; two alleged that they were unfit to participate for personal reasons that prevented them from attending the sessions. Thus, the present study consisted of a prospective, randomized, controlled clinical trial in which thirty-six women were followed up during the execution of the action. The sample calculation was based on the delimitation of type 1 error in 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), power in 80% ($1-\beta = 0.20$), under a two-tailed curve and effect size in 0, 50. By calculation, the ideal sample should be at least 28 subjects. This fact guided us in the initial screening of 36 subjects, as shown in figure 1.

Inclusion criteria were women aged 18 years and 38 years, eutrophic, non-smokers, non-alcoholic (according to their report), without diagnosis of dermatological disease or previous facial surgery (for at least 5 years), neurological disorders, or endocrine-metabolic, with phototype I to VI according to the classification of Fitzpatrick^[15] and with a complaint of oiliness and mild to moderate facial hyperpigmentation confirmed by the Baumann questionnaire^[16]. Pregnant, nursing, natives and quilombolas, women who have undergone dermatological and / or aesthetic treatment on the face in the last 6 months, or who have active face infection (acne > grade II), dermatological or metabolic disease which causes hyperpigmentation in the face, such as Cushing's Syndrome and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus or hyperpigmentation since birth, such as nevi. Those who could not attend the treatment and refused to carry out the proposed treatment or voluntarily desist. Using these criteria, the initial sample suffered considerable losses, starting with 36 participants, randomly divided into three groups by a lot of opaque envelopes, and faults of more than 25% of the sessions, ending with 30 participants, as described in figure 1.

Research participants were previously informed about data collection procedures. All signed a free and informed consent form. The evaluations and re-evaluations were carried out by an evaluator with the expertise to do so. Initially, anamnesis was carried out and soon after the procedures to evaluate the degree of oiliness of the skin, determined by the score of skin texture that graduated from 0 to 3, being zero no oiliness and three severe oiliness^[17].

The extent of post-acne hyperpigmentation was assessed by calculating the surface area of hyperpigmentation by decal. The

Figure 1:

right and left cheek and forehead were each made up to 30% each, and the chin accounted for 10%. After this, the photographic record was made using a digital camera (Sony HX100, 30x optical zoom) in the sagittal plane, two photographs (left and right hemiface) for each patient, with authorization previously signed by the same through the Authorization Form of Image Usage.

At the end of the 7th week, the analysis of the photographic evaluation of each participant was carried out by a specialist in the area, who classified the before and after photos in: without improvement (0), poor (1-25%), regular (25-50%), good (50-75%) and excellent (75-100%).

To assess participants' self-satisfaction regarding their treatment, participants were asked to report treatment outcome and efficacy through the Global Aesthetic Improvement Scale (GAIS) 17. This scale ranges from -1 to 3 points, being 3 much better (optimal cosmetic result in this patient), 2- much better (marked improvement in appearance from the initial condition, but not totally optimal), 1- better (improvement in appearance since the initial condition, but re-treatment is indicated) 0- no change (appearance essentially equal to the initial condition) and -1- worse (looks worse than the initial condition).

To assess tolerability to treatment, the participant was asked to assess the degree of irritation, or burning immediately the application of the proposed protocol on a scale of four options: 0 - itching or burning absent, 1- itching or light burning, 2- itching or moderate burning, 3- severe itching or burning^[17].

The participants in the R group were 10 women submitted to 3 bi-weekly sessions of 5% Retinoic Acid Pelling. The M-group comprised 10 women submitted to 3 biweekly sessions of Pelling of Mandelic Acid at 30%; and the group L-composed of 10 women submitted to three bi-weekly facial cleansing sessions (hygienization, exfoliation, extraction and toning). The patient remained in dorsal decubitus, eyes closed, bedside elevated at 45o, hair was held with disposable cap. To prevent acid buildup in the region peripheral of the eyes, used vaseline in cream in the lateral and medial region of the eyelids and lips.

The retinoic acid was applied according to the protocol of Magalhães, 2018, which uses the product with neutracolor, 5%, applied to the face with a brush in a thin layer lasting 60 minutes. After that, the product was removed with plenty of water and liquid soap. The acid was neutralized with a solution of water and 10% sodium bicarbonate. After that, the sunscreen was applied to 70%.

Mandelic acid was applied according to the Wojcik protocol, 2013, which uses the gel product, 30%, applied to the face with a brush in a thin layer and lasting 15 minutes. Soon after the product was removed with plenty of water and liquid soap. The acid was neutralized with a solution of water and 10% sodium bicarbonate. After that, the sunscreen was applied to 70%. The skin cleansing was composed of: cleaning with liquid soap (2 minutes), mechanical exfoliation (applied with circular movements on the face for 2 minutes), removal of waste with water, and toning applied with gauze on the face for 2 minutes, the products used are of the brand Vita Derm.

All women in the present study were instructed to report possible adverse effects of acids such as hyperemia, hypo or hyperpigmentation of the treated area. They also received guidelines to use the sun protection factor 70% daily, at home, with reapplications every 3 hours. They have been banned from using cosmetics during the flaking phase, exposing themselves to the sun, to the sauna or directly to the heat of the stove or oven without the proper protection.

This clinical trial was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS) under protocol number 61364816.0.0000.0021 and subsequently registered and approved in the Brazilian Registry of Clinical Trials (REBEC) under the code RBR-6D9657.

Statistical analysis

The comparison between the experimental groups, about age, the extent of hyperpigmentation and the photographic evaluation, were performed through the one-way ANOVA test, followed by the Student-Newman-Keuls post-test. The comparison between the experimental groups, in relation to the phototype, the evaluation of Glogau, the evaluation of the texture of the skin before and after the treatment and the GAIS score, was performed using the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test, with post-Dunn test when necessary, since the samples did not pass the Shapiro-Wilk normality test. The comparison between the experimental groups about the discomfort evaluation, in the three sessions to which the subjects were submitted, was performed through the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test. The comparison between the moments before and after the session in each experimental group, about the assessment of the skin texture, was performed using the Wilcoxon nonparametric test, whereas the comparison between the sessions in each experimental group was performed using the Friedman test, followed by the Dunn post-test. Finally, the evaluation of the association between the experimental group and the classification of the phototype variables, Glogau's evaluation and the extension of hyperpigmentation was performed using the chi-square test [19]. The other results of this study were presented in the form of descriptive statistics or the form of table and graph. Statistical analysis was performed using the statistical program SigmaPlot, version 12.5, considering a level of significance of 5%.

Results

Thirty healthy, eutrophic women with oily and hyperpigmented skin with a mean age of 22.17 ± 0.80 years participated in this study.

Table 1 shows the results for the different variables evaluated in this study, according to the experimental group. There was no difference between the experimental groups in relation to the age of the volunteers (one-way ANOVA test, $p = 0.848$), the score in the phototype evaluation (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 0.887$), the Glogau score (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 1,000$), to the extent of hyperpigmentation (one-way ANOVA test, $p = 0.988$) and to the skin texture evaluation score both before and after treatment (Kruskal-Wallis test, before: $p = 0.238$, then: $p = 0.207$). On the other hand, the score in the evaluation of discomfort in volunteers submitted to mandelic acid treatment was significantly higher than the score observed in volunteers submitted to retinoic acid treatment in the three treatment sessions (Mann-Whitney test, $p < 0.001$ in all sessions). In addition, there was a difference between the sessions, in relation to the score in the discomfort evaluation, in the volunteers submitted to mandelic acid treatment (Friedman test, $p = 0.002$), and in the second session this score was higher than that presented by the volunteers in the first session (Dunn post-test, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 2: Box plot chart illustrating the GAIS score, for each of the experimental groups evaluated. The horizontal line in bold represents the median, the box represents the interquartile range and the vertical bar represents the range of variation between the minimum and the maximum. * Significant difference in relation to the group of volunteers treated only with skin cleansing (Dunn post-test, $p < 0.05$).

Regarding the GAIS score, there was a significant difference between the experimental groups (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p = 0.002$), and this score was higher in volunteers treated with mandelic acid and retinoic acid when compared to volunteers submitted to skin cleansing (Dunn post-test, $p < 0.05$). These results are illustrated in Figure 2.

There was no significant association between the experimental group (treatment) and the classification of the phototype variables (chi-square test, $p = 0.690$), Glogau's evaluation ($p = 1,000$) and extension of hyperpigmentation ($p = 0.980$).

However, there was a significant difference between the experimental groups in relation to the photographic evaluation score (one-way ANOVA test, $p = 0.034$), and the mean score in patients treated with mandelic acid and retinoic acid was significantly higher than that observed in patients treated only with skin cleansing (Student-Newman-Keuls post-test, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1 Results referring to the different variables evaluated in this study, according to the experimental group.

Variable	Experimental Group			P value
	LP	mandélic A	retinoic A	
Age (18-36 years)	22,50±1,64	22,50±1,44	21,50±1,13	0,848
Marital status				
Marriage	20,0 (2)	20,0 (2)	10,0 (1)	0,787
Single	80,0 (8)	80,0 (8)	90,0 (9)	
Fototype	III (II a IV)	III (I a III)	III (II a IV)	0,897
I	0,0 (0)	10,0 (1)	0,0 (0)	
II	50,0 (5)	30,0 (3)	40,0 (4)	
III	40,0 (4)	60,0 (6)	50,0 (5)	
IV	10,0 (1)	0,0 (0)	10,0 (1)	
Glogau Score	II (I a II)	II (I a II)	II (I a II)	
I	20,0 (2)	20,0 (2)	20,0 (2)	
II	80,0 (8)	80,0 (8)	80,0 (8)	
III	0,0 (0)	0,0 (0)	0,0 (0)	
IV	0,0 (0)	0,0 (0)	0,0 (0)	
Hyperpigmentation area	62,00±5,93	61,11±6,55	63,00±3,96	0,988
30%	10,0 (1)	10,0 (1)	0,0 (0)	
40%	10,0 (1)	10,0 (1)	10,0 (1)	
60%	50,0 (5)	50,0 (5)	60,0 (6)	0,980
70%	10,0 (1)	10,0 (1)	20,0 (2)	
90%	20,0 (2)	20,0 (2)	10,0 (1)	
Assessment of skin texture				
Before	1 (1 a 2)	2 (1 a 3)	2 (1 a 2)	0,238
After	1 (1 a 2)	2 (1 a 3)	2 (1 a 2)	0,207
Valor de p	0,844	0,750	1,000	
Discomfort evaluation				
Session 1	-	1 (0 a 2)Ab	0 (0 a 0)Ba	<0,001
Session 2	-	2 (1 a 3)Aa	0 (0 a 1)Ba	<0,001
Session 3	-	1 (0 a 2)Aab	0 (0 a 0)Ba	<0,001
P value		0,002	0,050	
GAIS Score	0 (0 a 2)B	2 (1 a 3)A	2 (0 a 2)A	0,002
Photographic evaluation	49,50±6,26B	75,00±6,50A	69,50±7,73A	0,034

The results are presented in mean ± standard error of the mean or in median (minimum to maximum) or still in relative frequency (absolute frequency). The values of p presented are in the one-way ANOVA test, followed by the Student-Newman-Keuls post-test (between groups for age, extension of hyperpigmentation and photographic evaluation), in the Kruskal-Wallis test (between groups for phototype, Glogau, skin texture at each time point and GAIS), the Mann-Whitney test (between groups in the assessment of discomfort), the Wilcoxon test (times), the Friedman test (between sessions), the chi-square test (association between group and variables marital status, phototype, Glogau and hyperpigmentation). Different capital letters in the row indicate significant difference between the experimental groups ($p < 0.05$). Different lowercase letters in the column indicate significant difference between sessions in the evaluation of discomfort ($p < 0.05$). Significant p values are highlighted in bold ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3: Graph presenting the score in the photographic evaluation, in the patients of each of the experimental groups evaluated in this study. Each column represents the mean and bar the standard error of the mean. * Significant difference compared to patients in the group treated only with skin cleansing. (Student-Newman-Keuls post-test, $p < 0.05$).

These results are illustrated in Figure 3.

Discussion

The women in the present study were young (mean age 22.17 ± 0.80 years), of low income, had moderate post-acne hyperpigmentation and moderate facial oiliness, were eutrophic, non-smokers, non-alcoholic. Post-inflammatory hyperpigmentations appear in many dermatological conditions, including acne, eczema, and contact dermatitis. Inflammatory hyperpigmentations after acne are a problem for adult women because of their high prevalence and consequent negative repercussions on self-esteem/self-image and quality of life[20]. In this scenario, treatments that promote the acceleration of epidermis renewal, promoting greater homogeneity of skin colour, reducing brightness and producing improved self-image satisfaction and female quality of life are notorious[21].

A variety of topical agents are used to treat hyperpigmentation. These agents may interfere with the pigmentation process in different ways. The gold standard for treating this type of hyperpigmentation is a chemical agent called hydroquinone. Hydroquinone acts by inhibiting the conversion of dihydroxyphenylalanine to melanin by the inhibition of tyrosinase activity. As its use is topical, at concentrations of 2 to 4%, at home and night, it has low adherence and results in the long term, is often associated with retinoic acid to potentiate its effects and increase efficacy[22]. The other most used bleaching agents are azelaic acid, kojic acid and mandelic acid[23].

The objective of this study was to compare the cosmetic results, self-satisfaction and tolerability of treatment with 5% retinoic acid and 30% mandelic acid in adult women with post-acne hyperpigmentation. The results showed benefits obtained in groups M and R, submitted to mandelic and retinoic acids, compared to group L, submitted to skin cleansing, the same researcher treated all three groups. Moreover, all the evaluations were performed by another researcher, blind about the groups.

Regarding the physical evaluation, the groups were homogeneous regarding age, marital status, phototype, evaluation of Glogau photoaging, an extension of hyperpigmentation and skin texture, (oiliness - dryness). These data are essential, since they show the similarity between the groups, and it makes it

possible to analyze more clearly the benefits generated by the treatments.

The analysis of the discomfort score showed that mandelic acid promoted more considerable discomfort than retinoic acid in all sessions. The discomfort was higher in the second application session than in the first mandelic acid. This is due to the facts: 1) Retinoic acid is not a Ph drug dependent, and hence the solubility of the drug in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 to 4.0 which are higher than the pH used in the composition of mandelic acid in the gel (pH 3.5). 2) in the second application, the corneal layer of the epidermis is destroyed, and in the first session, it is integrated[24].

Analysis of the GAIS score showed that the M and R group obtained a significant improvement over the L group, which confirms the satisfaction of the participants regarding the cosmetic aspect of the face treated with both types of acids. The chemical abrasion obtained by the controlled application of acids in the epidermis stimulates corneal layer desquamation and the production of new cells, improving the quality and amount of collagen and glycosaminoglycans of the reticular dermis. This cellular renewal, due to the process of exfoliation that reduces the corneal layer of the skin, causes dispersion of the melanin granules within the keratinocytes, promoting celerity in the reepithelialization[25]. The action of these acids proved to reflect directly on the improvement of global aesthetics. Still, on the GAIS scale, both groups presented $p = 0.002$, with the median graded 2, which means in the scale: marked improvement in appearance from the initial condition, but not optimal for this patient. At this level of scoring the participant evaluates that there is no need for re-treatment. Considering that there are only three biweekly sessions, both protocols have reached the proposed goal. Since in clinical practice, the need for one or two peeling sessions should be evaluated individually.

It is important to note that retinoic acid is only used for medical professionals, and its maximum dosage is 10% at the outpatient level, and it is widely used for facial hyperpigmentation, melasma and photoaging[26]. The physical and chemical properties of mandelic acid, as well as glycolic acid[27], can be used in higher concentrations[28] and higher phototypes[29].

However, the application time reduced (15 to 30 minutes) and with direct supervision of the health professional to avoid areas of frosting. Also, in acidic medium, mandelic acid has bacteriostatic and bactericidal properties, especially for the bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus proteus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Aerobacter aerogenes*[30]. All health professionals can use mandelic acid. Thus, a good alternative for the physiotherapist specialized in dermatofunctional physiotherapy to act safely and effectively on inflammatory hyperpigmentations post-acne[9]. There are not many studies on the application of the superficial peeling of mandelic acid in the literature. The study by Garg and Sinha[24] demonstrated the effectiveness of mandelic acid in whitening facial hyperpigmentation in patients resistant to bleaching with other conventional treatment modalities. He compared the therapeutic efficacy and tolerability of 35% glycolic acid versus 10% salicylic-10% mandelic acid, the latter being superior.

Wójcik's study[14] demonstrated that mandelic acid was shown to be effective in promoting the increase of sebaceous secretion in the skin of mature women as a resource for the treatment of photoaging, loss of elasticity and dryness of facial skin that commonly occurs after menopause due to hypoestrogenism. He compared 40% mandelic acid with 20% azelaic acid

in women with FitzPatrick type II and III and Glogau type III and IV. Both acids were considered effective, safe and well tolerated in women with photoaging. Both reduced the effects of skin ageing, especially in dryness, regulating sebaceous secretion, especially in the U-zone of the face. Both protocols showed good adherence to the treatment by the volunteers, as there were only two losses in each group, totalling six withdrawal participants. The ease of application of both protocols in a favourable environment cooperated for the recruitment of the number of target volunteers.

The limitations of the research should not be neglected, in the first place, the scarcity of studies on this subject should be highlighted, is essential to emphasize that only individuals with oiliness and hyperpigmentation verified using the Baumann questionnaire[16], in the section Oil with punctuation between 27 to 44. Another interesting fact was the safety of these peeling protocols, measured by the occurrence of a few mild and transient adverse events, such as erythema and discomfort, and occurred in the post-peeling mediate.

Conclusion

The chemical agent treatment provides greater user satisfaction with cosmetic aspects of the skin when compared to manual mechanical exfoliation of the skin.

Mandelic acid was similar to retinoic acid in the whitening of lesions caused by acne, from the evaluator and the users. The short-term chemical peeling protocol is not effective in reducing the size of the hyperpigmentation area or reducing skin oiliness. For these effects, additional studies are required, investigating different concentrations or longer follow-up time.

Competing Interests

None

Ethics committee approval

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